

Development of vertical wind turbine blades using 4D printing of composites

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Abstract:

This paper presents the procedure to make vertical wind turbine blades using the technique of 4D printing of composites (4DPC). The blade is made using carbon/epoxy composite materials with fiber volume fraction of about 60%. Even though the blade has a 3D shape with curvatures, it is made using only a flat mold. The procedure can provide time and cost savings due to the fact that molds of complex curvature are not necessary. At the same time, the material is strong, stiff, and light giving further savings in weight and subsequent benefits in handling. Testing on wind turbines with original aluminum blades and with composite blades shows that the wind turbines with composite blades run at higher speeds. Also, wind turbine with composite blades gives higher efficiency than wind turbines with original aluminum blades.

Introduction:

Wind turbines are one source of generators of green energy. The majority of wind turbines are horizontal axis type, with very long blades and can generate a large amount of energy. Another type of wind turbine is the vertical axis wind turbine. These are smaller wind turbines. They are usually located on the roof of buildings. The amount of energy they generate is small but may be sufficient for energy needs in a small building. The global vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) market size accounted for USD \$12.9 billion in 2022, and is projected to achieve a market size of USD \$17.7 billion by 2032 growing at a CAGR of 3.2% from 2023 to 2032. According to research conducted by the National Renewable Energy Lab ((NREL) in the U.S., VAWTs provide more yearly energy per unit area than horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWT) [1].

One example of the vertical axis wind turbine is shown in Figure 1. This wind turbine is of RX-SV2 turbine from R & X Technology company in Nantong, China. The company specifications mention it exhibits a nominal power output of 200 Watts, a wheel diameter measuring 48 cm, and a weight of 15 kg. It utilizes 2 sets of aluminum blades, with each set comprising 5 individual segments. The segments are assembled around a vertical axis, facilitated by horizontal arms. It can be observed that the blades are configured with a backward twist to reach higher performance and harvest more energy. These blades may be made by roll forming, or hydraulic pressing techniques. Either of these techniques requires a mold.

Figure 1: One example of the vertical axis wind turbine

Technique of 4D printing of composites:

4D Printing of Composites (4DPC) is a technique of composite manufacturing that does not require a mold of complex geometry. It only requires a flat mold. As such it is also called Moldless Composite Manufacturing. The technique was conceived in 2017 [2]. To manufacture a structure with curved geometry, first, a stack of soft composite prepregs (such as carbon/epoxy) is laid on top of a flat mold. The deposition can be done either by hand (for simple lay-ups) or by the use of an automated fiber placement machine (AFP) for either simple or more complex lay-ups. The AFP machine does manufacturing in an additive fashion. In principle, it is similar to a 3D printer, except that it is much larger, and it can deposit strips of fiber-reinforced polymers in different directions. The lay-up sequence of the different layers in the stack is of critical importance. Rather than the usual symmetric lay-up sequences that have been used in most of the composite community, un-symmetric lay-ups are used. In the soft state of the prepregs, there is no interaction between the layers due to the difference in their fiber orientations. However, after these prepreg layers are heated to the cure temperature, the resin hardens and the layers become stiff. During the cooling process from cure temperature to room temperature, the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion between the layers along the different directions creates interaction between them. This interaction gives rise to the change in shape from flat to curved.

The 4DPC technique has been used to develop pieces with S shape [2], leaf springs [3], omega stiffeners [4], corrugated core for flexible aircraft wings [5], and conical shells (figure 2) [6]. The same concept of 4DPC is also used for the development of manufacturing of blades of the vertical axis wind turbine.

Figure 2: Conical shells made using the 4DPC technique. Left: Partial shell. Right: Complete shell [6].

Procedure to manufacture the blades of the vertical wind turbine using 4DPC:

Most of the structures presented in references [2-6] are of the forward type of problem. In the forward type of problem, some lay-up sequence is proposed, and the resulting structure is obtained. The procedure to make the blades for the vertical wind turbine follows a reverse type of problem. In the reverse type of problem, a structure with a certain shape and configuration is desired. The problem is to find the flat lay-up sequence such that when the stack of prepregs is cured and cooled to room temperature, the desired shape and configuration is obtained. This procedure consists of the following steps:

Step 1: Determination of the configuration of the existing (or desired) structure.

Step 2: Propose some lay-up sequence.

Step 3: Determination of the configuration of the structure resulting from the proposed lay-up sequence. At the initial stage, this can be a trial-and-error approach. After some experience, the trial-and-error process can be minimized.

Step 4: A final configuration that fits the most to the desired configuration is obtained.

Details of the above steps for the development of the blades of the vertical axis wind turbine using 4DPC are presented below.

Step 1: Determination of the configuration of the existing (or desired) structure

The two blades of the existing commercial wind turbine as shown in figure 1 consist of two similar blades. Each blade consists of 5 segments. Each segment is a curved piece. Figure 3 shows the 6 segments disassembled from the wind turbine. The focus of the work is to develop the procedure of manufacturing of one segment using 4DPC. Once this is accomplished, the other segments can be made the same way. They will then be assembled to make up the blade.

Figure 3: One segment of the blade in commercial wind turbine.

The overall dimensions of the segment is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Overall dimensions of a segment

Detailed configuration of one segment was obtained by scanning the segment using a laser projection machine as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: A segment in the laser projection machine. (a) Laser projection machine with laser mounted on top. (b) Segment on the base of the machine.

By adjusting the two probes on the right and front of the segment, the coordinates of various points on the surface can be measured, allowing for the complete generation of the surface of the segment. Two hundred points were measured. A sample of the data of 16 points is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample of the data for 16 points from coordinate measurements.

No.	x (mm)	y (mm)	z (mm)	No.	x (mm)	y (mm)	z (mm)
1	0	220	0	121	75.4	206.6	100
10	97.1	170.5	0	130	152.5	114.7	100
20	109.6	51.1	0	140	111.3	1.9	100
30	12.5	-19.3	0	150	5.15	-22.5	100
61	38.6	216.6	50	181	116.9	186.4	160
70	130.2	139.5	50	190	173	80.4	160
80	109.3	21.3	50	200	109.3	-21.3	160
90	8.9	-21.2	50	210	0.4	-23	160

The data collected were processed using the surface fitting tool in MATLAB software. This generates equation (1). The linear dimensions are in meter, and the angle is in radians.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 3.5 z] + 0.1 \sin[3.5 z] \\
 y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 3.5 z] + 0.1 \cos[3.5 z]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

Where z is the coordinate along the vertical direction, and θ is the polar coordinate in the horizontal plane. x and y are the coordinates in a plane parallel to the horizontal plane at elevation z . These are in meters.

The nature of the surface can be revealed by examining a few points using equation (1).

At $z = 0$ (the base plane), one has:

$$x = 0.12 \sin[\theta] \quad y = 0.12 \cos[\theta] + 0.1 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) represents that of a circle with radius of 0.12 m (120 mm) with center located at O_b (0, 100 mm) in the base horizontal x, y plane, as shown in figure 6. The axes are x_1 (parallel with x) and y_1 (coinciding with y). Note that the points at the base plane of the blade only occupy a portion of the circle with origin at O_b in the figure .

At $z = 10\text{mm}$ (0.01 m) in equation (1) one has:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 0.035] + 0.1 \sin[0.035] & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.035] + 0.1 \cos[0.035] \quad \text{or} \\ x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 0.035] + 0.0035 & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.035] + 0.1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) represents that of a circle with radius 120 mm with the origin at O_2 (3.5 mm, 100 mm). To keep the same boundary points as for the case of $z = 0$ mm, the coordinate axes are x_2, y_2 (rotated 0.035 radians (2.0°)) relative to the x, y axes. .

At $z = 20\text{ mm}$ (0.02 m), in equation (1) one has:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 0.07] + 0.1 \sin[0.07] & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.07] + 0.1 \cos[0.07] \quad \text{or} \\ x &= 120 \sin[\theta + 0.07] + 0.007 & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.07] + 0.1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) represents that of a circle with radius 120 mm with the origin at O_3 (7.0 mm, 100 mm). Again, to keep the same boundary points as in the case $z = 0$, the coordinate axes are x_3, y_3 (rotated 0.07 radians (4.0°)) relative to the x, y axes.

At $z = 165\text{ mm}$ (0.165 m), in equation (1) one has:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 0.5775] + 0.1 \sin[0.5775] & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.5775] + 0.1 \cos[0.5775] \\ \text{or} \\ x &= 0.12 \sin[\theta + 0.5775] + 0.055 & y &= 0.12 \cos[\theta + 0.5775] + 0.084 \end{aligned} \quad (5).$$

Equation (5) represents that of a circle with radius 120 mm with the origin at O_t (55mm, 84 mm). The coordinate axes are x_t, y_t (rotated 0.5775 radians (33.1°)) relative to the x, y axes. Note that $z = 165$ mm is at the top of the segment (subscript t). This circle is shown in figure 6.

It can be seen that even the radius of curvature of the blade remains the same as z changes, there is a shift in the center of the circle (mainly in the x direction). In order to keep the same boundary points in all cases, there is also a rotation of the axes. As such point A_b in the bottom plane moves to point A_t on the top plane (Note that figure 6 does not show the change in

elevation of the top circle). At the same time, point B_b moves to point B_t . The circular portion A_bB_b changes to $A_t B_t$. The rotation does not present a twist.

Figure 6: Curved lines connecting nodes 1 to 300 ($z = 0$ mm, bottom) and nodes 181 to 210 ($z = 165$ mm, top). Node numbers are shown in figure 7.

Using MATLAB, the whole surface of the blade as given by equation (1) is plotted and shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Plot of equation (1)

From the analysis of principal curvatures shows that the points can be classified into two groups (the edge group and the central region). The principal curvatures of these two groups are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Principal curvatures for two regions

	$K_1 (m^{-1})$	$K_2 (m^{-1})$
Left edge (nodes 1, 61, 121, 181)	9.5	1.07
Right edge (nodes 30, 90, 150, 210)	9.3	1.10
Central region (nodes 10, 20, 70, 80, 130, 140, 190, 200)	8.2	0.52

Table 2 shows that there is a large difference between the values of K_1 and K_2 . The small curvature of K_2 indicates that the structure is practically flat along this direction. As such, at any

point on the surface of the segment, cylindrical curvature exists. This means that there is no twist.

The above observations are used as guidelines for the determination of the lay-up sequence to make the segment structure using 4D printing of composites. The curvature of the central region (8.2 m^{-1}) is used as the main focus. In the following, a number of trial laminate sequences will be examined. Laminate theory will be used to determine the curvature from these laminates. The lay-up sequence yielding the closest value of curvature to 8.2 m^{-1} will be selected.

Step 2: Determination of the lay-up sequence:

The material used is carbon/epoxy prepreg (1409-D) supplied from Rockwest composites. The curing cycle is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Curing cycle for carbon/epoxy from Rockwest Composites

The material properties are shown in Table 3. These values were measured at the Concordia Center for Composites laboratories. The other properties are taken from reference [8] as: shear modulus $G_{12} = 4.4 \text{ GPa}$, and coefficient of thermal expansion $\alpha_1 = -0.018 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 3: Material properties

E_1 (GPa)	120.2
E_2 (GPa)	7.4
ν_{12}	0.219
α_2 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	33.33
Thickness of one ply (h) (mm)	0.165

The curvatures are calculated using laminate theory as described in reference [2]. A Matlab program was developed for this [9]. Table 4 shows the curvatures of the different laminates.

Table 4: Curvatures of different laminates

Laminate sequence	K_1 (m^{-1})	R_1 (mm)
[0/90]	11,4	74.6
[0/90 ₂]	9.2	92.6

$[0/90_3]$	9.1	110
$[0/90_4]$	7.8	128

Table 2 shows that the curvatures in the segment vary from 8.2 m^{-1} to 9.5 m^{-1} from the central region to the edges. From Table 4, both laminates with lay-up sequences $[0/90_2]$ and $[0/90_3]$ provide curvatures that fit within this window. For light weight consideration, laminates with lay-up sequence $[0/90_2]$ was selected.

Step 3: Procedure to lay-up the surface of the segment:

The flat blank, which is a development of the curved segment into a flat panel, is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: Flat blank as developed from the curved segment.

It was shown in the above section that as one moves along the x direction, it is necessary to rotate the x,y axes a few degrees in order to conform to the surface of the segment. In order to maintain the same radius of curvature, the same lay up sequence of $[0/90_3]$ needs to be maintained. In order to address the rotation, from a 4DPC point of view, the flat is divided into four sections. The lay up sequence is rotated a few degrees as one moves from segment 1 to segment 2 etc. Figure 10 shows the lay-up sequence after the rotation. Figure 11 shows the detailed dimensions of the sections.

Figure 10: Lay-up sequence in the four regions of the segment

Using the above procedure, the composite segment was matched up with the aluminum segment from the commercial wind turbine. Figure 11 shows the two pieces together (blue piece is aluminum). It can be seen that the two pieces match together fairly well for the majority of the surfaces. There is a slight mismatch at the left edge.

Figure 11: Comparison between the manufactured piece and the real segment.

After manufacturing all the segments, they were assembled to the central pole of the vertical axis wind turbine alongside with the aluminum blades. The final assembly of the wind turbine can be seen in figure 12.

Figure 12- The final assembly of the vertical axis wind turbine blades.

Conclusion

It was shown that it is possible to make wind turbine blades for vertical axis wind turbines using the technique of 4D Printing of Composites (4DPC). The segments of the blades made have similar shape as the aluminum segment of the original design. The new method is a moldless way of manufacturing, which provides savings in cost and time. The use of composite materials offers light weight which can improve efficiency of operation.

References:

1. Acumen researchandconsulting.com /vertical-axis-wind-turbine-market.
2. Hoa Suong Van, "Factors affecting the properties of composites made by 4D printing", *Advanced Manufacturing: Polymers and Composites Science*, 2017, 3, 1-9.
3. Suong Van Hoa, "Development of composite springs using 4D printing method", *Composite structures*, 210, 2019, pp. 869-876.
4. Suong V. Hoa, Bhargavi Reddy, Daniel Rosca, "Development of omega stiffeners using 4D printing of composites", *Composite Structures*, 272, 2021, 114264.
5. Suong Hoa, Marjan Abdali, Anick Jasmin, Daniel Radeschi, Victor Prats, Hadi Faour, Backer Kobaissi, "Development of a new flexible wing concept of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using corrugated core made by 4D printing of composites", *Composite Structures*, 290, 2022, 115444.
6. Suong Van Hoa and Mahmoud Fereidouni, "Conical shells made using 4D printing of composites", *Composites, Part A, Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 178, March 2024, 107971.
7. Toponogov VA. *Differential geometry of curves and surfaces*. Springer; 2006.
8. Hyer M.W. "Stress analysis of fiber reinforced composite materials+", Destech Publications, 2009.
9. Hoa Suong Van, "4D printing of composites", De Gruyter, 2025.